

Plain language summary

Background

Osteoporosis is a bone disease that causes bones to become weak and fragile. This can lead to fractures happening more easily. It is most common in women who have gone through the menopause (postmenopausal).

We investigated the current evidence about screening for osteoporosis in postmenopausal women. There is currently no national screening programme for osteoporosis in the UK.

Our approach

We sought to answer the following questions:

- 1.(a) How much evidence is there that screening all women over 65 for osteoporosis helps prevent fractures, compared to their usual care?
- 1.(b) How much evidence is there that screening women under 65 with risk factors for osteoporosis helps prevent fractures, compared to their usual care?
2. How much evidence is there on the cost-effectiveness of osteoporosis screening?
3. How are health inequalities considered in research around osteoporosis screening?

We sought opinions from a group of people who bring their carer, patient, or public perspective to our research. Their input helps ensure that the research is relevant and accessible.

Our findings

We found 19 studies that fit our inclusion criteria, including four clinical studies and six reviews. The studies generally included all women 65 and older and looked at different screening methods. Studies reported outcomes including fractures, quality of life and cost-effectiveness of screening, and some considered health inequalities.

Our conclusions

There is a relatively small amount of evidence on the effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of osteoporosis screening, which mainly looks at all women over 65, rather than women under 65 with risk factors. Most of the available evidence does not consider the impact of health

inequalities. More research, with a greater focus on health inequalities, is needed to help policymakers make decisions about screening.